

New Scientific Staff at NOIRLab

Kathy Vivas (NOIRLab)

Ten new astronomers were recruited this spring to join the NOIRLab scientific staff. They will support a wide variety of programs over all of the NOIRLab locations. This is the first time that NOIRLab's

Research and Science Services has performed an integrated recruitment program aimed at hiring scientific staff. The goal was to not only fulfill specific needs for service roles throughout NOIRLab but also strengthen the scientific capabilities of NOIRLab.

Guillermo Damke (see profile in "A Reflection of His Father" on page 10 of this issue) and **Aleksandar Cikota** have joined the scientific staff in La Serena, bringing new capabilities to the CTIO and Gemini programs, respectively. Guillermo is an expert on astrophysics with applications

to both galaxy classification and stellar populations in the Milky Way. He is also involved in research regarding the preservation of dark skies in Chile. Aleksandar brings spectropolarimetry expertise to

NOIRLab. His research interests include Type Ia Supernova progenitors and supernova cosmology, dust extinction in supernova hosts, and superluminous supernovae.

Two new scientific staff in Hilo have been assigned to service roles at Gemini Observatory. **Garima Singh** is an expert on adaptive optics and direct imaging of extrasolar planets. She is expected to continue playing an important role with the Gemini Planet Imager-2.0 (GPI-2.0) instrument currently in development for Gemini North. **David Jones** has joined the Gemini Science User Support Department. His research focuses on Type Ia supernovae and their implications for cosmology, including the expansion rate of the local Universe, as parameterized by the Hubble constant, and the expansion history as a means of probing the nature of dark energy.

Guillermo Damke

Aleksandar Cikota

Garima Singh

David Jones

Four scientific staff have joined NOIRLab in Tucson. **Eric Peng** comes to NOIRLab with wide experience in the study of the formation of galaxies using nearby “fossil” stellar populations. He has served on the Thirty Meter Telescope Science Advisory Committee and as the Project Scientist for TMT’s Wide Field Optical Spectrometer. At NOIRLab, Eric will be helping to shape the US ELT Program.

Yuanyuan Zhang is an expert on extended low-surface-brightness light in galaxy clusters, large-scale structures, cosmology, and wide-field imaging surveys. She has been assigned to service roles in the Community Science and Data Center

Eric Peng

Christina Williams

Yuanyuan Zhang

Ryan Lau

(CSDC). **Christina Williams** and **Ryan Lau** are now part of the Rubin Community Engagement Team. Ryan will also be spending part of his time in CSDC, to bolster its role in supporting the use of Rubin data. Ryan works on the evolution and death of massive stars and their enrichment of the interstellar medium (ISM). He is particularly interested in the role of Wolf-Rayet stars as potential leading sources of dust in the ISM of galaxies, a project that he is pursuing with the JWST. Christina uses data from the X-ray through radio wavelengths to study how galaxies form and evolve. She is also a member of the JWST NIRCcam science team.

We expect two additional science staff members to arrive at NOIRLab in 2023.